

INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA CHOY KOMPONENTLI FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLARNING CHOG'ISHTIRMA TADQIQI

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ANNOTATSIYA:

Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarida choy komponentli frazeologik birliklarning tadqiqi haqida so'z yuritilgan. Frazeologik birliklar hamma tilning imkoniyatlarini namoyon qiladi. Frazeologik birliklar qatorida choy komponentli frazeologik birliklarning o'rni alohida. Maqolada choy komponentli frazeologik birliklarning tarjimasi, ularning ikki tilda muqobillari va ularning ishlatilishi haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: fraza, frazeologik birliklar, leksik ma'no, frazeologik chatishma.

ANNOTATION:

This article discusses the study of phraseological units with the component of tea in English and Uzbek. Phraseological units demonstrate the capabilities of any language. Among phraseological units, phraseological units with the tea component occupy a special place. The article discusses the translation of phraseological units with the tea component, their alternatives in both languages, and their use.

Keywords: phrase, phraseological units, lexical meaning, phraseological combination..

Dunyoda suvdan keyin turuvchi ommabop ichimlik bu choy hisoblanadi. Choy kundalik hayotning ajarmas qismi bo'lganligi tufayli ingliz xalqida ham, o'zbek xalqida ham choy bilan bog'liq iboralarni kuzatishimiz mumkin. Quyida bir necha choy komponentli frazeologik birliklar tahlilini ko'ramiz.

Choy nafaqat ichimlik, balki madaniyatning bir ko'rinishi hamdir. Har ikkala tilda ham choy komponentli frazeologik birliklarni ko'rishimiz mumkin. O'zbek xalqi uchun choy kunning boshlanishidir. Dasturxon yozilganda albatta choy va juft non qo'yiladi. O'zbek xalqining asosiy ichimligi sanalmish choy ingliz xalqining ham sevimli ichimligi hisoblanadi. Ularda choy bilan bog'lik marosimlar ham mavjud.

Buyuk Britaniyada choyning tarixi haqida qisqacha.

Buyuk Britaniya XVIII asrdan boshlab dunyodagi eng yirik choy iste'molchilari qatoriga kirgan. Dastlab u faqat yuqori tabaqa vakillari tomonidan

sevib ichildiga ichimlik bo'lgan bo'lsada, keyinchalik u asta-sekin Buyuk Britaniyadagi barcha tabaqa vakillarining sevimli, odatiy ichimligiga aylandi. Choy Britaniya madaniyatining o'ziga xos qismidir. XXI asrda bir piyola choy oddiy ichimlik sanalsa, XVII-XVIII asrlard siyosiy, ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy ta'sirga ega bo'lgan. Kundalik hayotida choy ichimligi bilan ko'p yuzlashgan bu ikki xalqda ham choy bilan bog'liq iboralarni kuzatishimiz mumkin. Not my cup of tea –bu so'zlovchining didiga mos kelmaslikni bildiruvchi ibora. “My cup of tea” va “not my cup of tea” iboralari Buyuk Britaniyada va ingliz tilida so'zlashadigan boshqa xalqlar orasida ham keng tarqalgan. “A cup of tea” iborasi 20-asrning boshlarida maqbullikning sinonimiga aylandi. Bu ibora shunchalik ommalashdiki, bu yaxshi do'stga yoki xushmanzara tabiatga nisbatan aytilardi. Taxminan 1930-yillarda odamlar o'zlari yoqtirgan narsalarni “my cup of tea” deb ta'riflay boshladilar. Bu 1932 yilda Nensi Mitfordning “Christmas pudding” komik romanida aks etadi: “I'm not at all sure I wouldn't rather marry Aunt Loudie. She's even more my cup of tea in m/any ways.” Ushbu iboraga dastlab ijobiy shaklini ishlatilgan bo'lsa-da, bugungi kunda “not my cup of tea” tarzida ko'proq foydalaniladi.

Husband's tea-weak tea- bu iboraning kelib chiqishi quidagicha faraz mavjud. Yomon ayol hamma choyni o'zi ichib qo'yib, turmush o'rtog'iga suv solib berishi bilan izohlanadi. Bu juda kam solingan choy- kuchsiz choy.

Not for all the tea in China- bu ibora biror ish harakatni bajarmaslik uchun inkorni ifodalaydi. Ya'ni shu ishni Xitoyning hamma choyni evaziga ham bajarmasligini ifodalaydi. O'zbek tiliga tarjoma qilganimizda hech qachon yoki hech narsa evaziga deb tarjima qilsak bo'ladi. O'zbek tilida bu frazaga muqobilini ko'

I wouldn't trust that salesman for all the tea in China. He is trying to rob us- Men bu sotuvchiga ishonmayman. U bizni tunamoqchi.

I won't go out in this weather for all the tea in China- men bu havoda ko'chaga chiqmayman.

As good as a chocolate teapot- Shakaladdan qilingan choynakka issiq suv quyilayotganini tasavvur qiling. Shakalad tezda erib ketadi va issiq suv atrofga sachraydi. Shunday ekan biror narsa haqiqatdan foydasiz bo'lsa ushbu iboradan foydalaniladi.

A car without petrol is as good as a chocolate teapot- Yoqilg'isiz moshina huddi shakaladdan qilingan choynak kabidir.

Have you heard of shoe umbrellas? They are as useful as a chocolate teapot- Poyabzal soyabonlari haqida eshitdingizmi? Ular shakaladdan qilingan choynakdek

foydalidir.

Ya'ni bu yerda

inkor ma'no mavjud.

Spill the tea- bu ibora bironing sirini ochish yoki g'iybatini qilish ma'nosini anglatadi.

Come on, spill the tea, what's Rob's new girlfriend like?- Bo'laqol, sirni och, Robning yangi qiz o'rtog'ining ko'rinishi qanaqa?

Read the tea leaves- ba'zi odamlar choy idishi ichidagi choy qoldiqlariga qarab kelajakni bashorat qilish mumkin deb ishonishadi. Bu ibora narsalarga qarab bashorat qilishni ifodalaydi.

We don't need to read the tea leaves to understand that the company will go bankrupt soon- Kampaniyaning tez orada bankrot bo'lishini bashorat qilish shart emas.

Xulosa. Har ikkala tilda ham choy bilan bog'liq frazeologik birliklarni ko'rishimiz mumkin. Choy bilan bog'liq frazeologik birliklarning tub ma'nosida har doim ham choy bilan bog'liq bo'lavermaydi.

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